

A Local Study on the Effects of L-Carnitine Supplement on Serum Lipid Profiles in Libyan Type 2 Diabetic Patients

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes is a complex set of diseases that require continuous medical care and patient self-management education to control blood sugar and to prevent the risk of long-term complications. The main aim of this current research study was to investigate the lipid lowering effects of L-carnitine (LC) supplementation in Libyan type 2 diabetic patients. This research study was conducted on sixty (60) subjects that were selected from El-beida Diabetic Center, Libya within selected criteria. The patients divided into three groups (control group of healthy people and two groups of diabetic patients who were on metformin and glibenclamide, one group took a LC in a dose of 1000 mg twice daily and a group dealing with a placebo for a period of three months continuously). The study found that the patients who took LC, showed a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in the triglyceride (TG) level, while no significant changes were observed in the levels of total cholesterol (TC), high density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL-C), and low density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL-C). This study concluded that the administration of LC improved the lipid profile in type 2 diabetic patients.

Keyword: L-carnitine (LC), lipid profiles, dyslipidemia, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), El-beida, Libya

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a global health issue affecting children, adolescents, and adults. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 180 million people worldwide currently have T2DM (formerly called adult-onset diabetes); over 95% of people with diabetes have this form (1). WHO has recently proposed new diagnostic criteria and classification of DM. A major change in diagnostic criteria is lowering of diagnostic fasting plasma glucose (FPG) level to less than 7mmol/L (2). It is associated with long-term damage, dysfunction, and failure of different organs (3). Diabetes is associated with both micro vascular and macro vascular diseases affecting several organs, including muscle, skin, heart, brain, and kidneys (4). The terms type 1 and type 2 are used for classification based on etiology. The terms insulin-dependent and non-insulin dependent are used for pathophysiological staging of diabetes mellitus regardless of the etiology (5).

The prevalence of diabetes for all age-groups world-wide was estimated to be 2.8% in 2000 and 4.4% in 2030. The number of people with diabetes

is increasing due to population growth, aging (6), urbanization (7), and increasing prevalence of obesity and physical inactivity. L-carnitine is a natural nutrient co-factor required for transport of long-chain fatty acids into the mitochondria, where they undergo β -oxidation to produce adenosine triphosphate (ATP) for cellular energy production which is a primary fuel source for proper function in many tissues and prevent the toxic accumulation of long-chain fatty acids (8).

1.1. Role of L-carnitine in the T2DM

Patients with T2DM seem to be at elevated risk for carnitine deficiency (9). High levels of L-carnitine short-circuit the Randle cycle by sequestering inhibitory acetyl-CoA units as acetyl-carnitine and concomitantly increasing free CoA levels. Lowering of the mitochondrial acetyl-CoA:CoA ratio would then favor glucose oxidation (16). L-carnitine-mediated sequestering of toxic lipid metabolites may have benefited both mitochondrial performance and insulin signaling (10). LC can also play a role in the treatment of type 2 diabetics by improving insulin resistance that is caused by post-receptors defect. This means that LC may be useful for cell membrane

repairing and, removal of harmful lipid from the cells may improve or decrease the resistance to insulin action by photoreceptor defect either at the membrane or intracellular level (11). Administration of LC may shift the metabolic bias of the liver away from esterification and synthesis of triglycerides toward the formation of acetylcarnitines. This could decrease synthesis of triglycerides and VLDL cholesterol and likely increase mitochondrial β -oxidation of fatty acids (12).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was done in El-beida Diabetic Center, Libya from May 2019 to August 2019 on 60 subjects (41 male and 19 female) with age range 40-64 years in nonrandomized method. All participants follow inclusion and exclusion criteria.

2.1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for participants

The inclusion criteria for healthy subjects were to be free from other chronic diseases or drugs, while diabetic patients were to be poor controlled T2DM for at least 6 years and more, on metformin and glibenclamide therapy, and had lipid profile disorder. This study excluded the pregnant, breast-feeding, and post-menopausal women. It also excluded smokers, alcohol drinkers, and those with liver, kidney, epileptic, and thyroid diseases.

The participants were divided into three groups as follows:

Group (1): It Included 20 apparently healthy individuals (16 male and 4 females) as control.

Group (2): It included 20 diabetic patients (10 males and 10 females). This group was taken L-carnitine 1000 mg tablets twice daily for three months.

Group (3): It Included 20 diabetic patients (15 male and 5 females) were treated with placebo for three months.

Blood samples were taken from all individuals included in this study at the baseline time and every 30 days of the study period. Blood was collected by venipuncture technique in order to measure serum lipid profiles.

Statistical analysis was performed by using unpaired student T-test between healthy individuals and diabetic patients (whether placebo group or L-carnitine group), and paired student T-test between zero time, after 1st, 2nd and 3rd month in all groups involved in this study.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the effects of LC on the serum lipid profiles, involving TC, TG, HDL-C, and LDL-C. Concerning the TC, the outcome of trial showed non-significant changes observed in the treated group as well as placebo during the study period, meanwhile, the data expressed a significant reduction of serum TG from 1st month in comparison with baseline value, at ($p < 0.05$) and highly significant at the 2nd month and 3rd month respectively. Table 1 also shows non-significant changes in the HDL-C and LDL-C at the 3 months of the study period whether in treated group or placebo.

Table 1: The effects of treatment with L-carnitine on serum lipid profiles in T2DM patients (n=20)

Parameter groups	Regime	TC (mg/dl)	TG (mg/dl)	HDL-C (mg/dl)	LDL-C (mg/dl)
Control	Baseline	183.50±33.10*	154.70±41.10*	40.90±5.95	85.72±13.50 ^a
Placebo	Baseline	208.90±30.81 ^b	173.60 ±49.73 ^b	39.90±8.23	127.41±27.12 ^b
	1month	206.69±32.50	176.70±51.32	38.94±5.38	127.32±26.15
	2month	208.40±39.00	177.68 ±49.20	39.98±7.58	126.51 ±25.60
	3month	207.37± 21.20	173.22±35.61	40.01±5.25	124.90±17.20
Treatment with LC	Baseline	201.81±24.52 ^b	174.63±38.90 ^b	40.05± 6.60	120.11±22.60 ^b
	1month	202.10±25.91	164.34±30.93*	39.90 ±5.29	122.13±23.70
	2month	201.70±22.42	158.10± 28.17*	40.01±5.12	121.20±20.50
	3month	200.70±27.40	147.96±26.62*	40.19±4.96	120.20±21.20

a, b: represent statistically significant change ($p < 0.05$) for comparison between healthy group and diabetic groups (on placebo or on L-carnitine).

*****: represents statistically significant change ($p < 0.05$) for comparison between pre and post treatment values of treated groups.

N: number of individuals.

4. DISCUSSION

The current study demonstrated a non-significant decline in the serum TC, HDL-C, and LDL-C levels in the treated group after one, two, and three months of treatment in comparison with zero time readings, and this may be due to a fact that LC does not have direct potent effect on the cholesterol synthesis pathway, or the period of trial was not sufficient to observe such a change. This observation was consistent with that obtained by Gonzalez-Ortiz et al., (2008) (10), Golbidi et al., (2011) (11), and Roberto et al., (2012) (12). However, these findings disagreed with other studies who observed positive effects of L-carnitine supplementation on total cholesterol (13,14,16,17), while Irat et al., (2003) (15) suggested that the beneficial effects of L-carnitine treatment partially improve vascular reactivity and antioxidant property beyond its

reduction of plasma lipids and it may have an important therapeutic approach in the treatment of diabetic vascular complications (18). It also considers a good adjuvant therapy beside cholesterol-lowering drugs (statins) for its mechanism that reverses the myopathy which is possible side effect of cholesterol-lowering drugs and potentiated statin effect (19).

LC may also have a qualitative effect on HDL-C rather than increase level of the former through improve the integrity that carries important antioxidant enzymes (paraoxanase and platelet activating factor acetylhydrolase) which serve to protect from oxidation and increase half-life of HDL-C (20), while another study showed that LC caused a significant twofold increase in α -tocopherol (vitamin E) content in oxidized LDL-C and caused a reduction in the level of conjugated dienes, lipid hydroperoxide, malondialdehyde,

and dityrosine (21). The present study found a successful improvement and significant decline in the triglyceride level in the treated group in comparison with baseline readings, and this may be due to the L-carnitine effects on free fatty acid (FFA) metabolism, glucose hemostasis, improvement in insulin sensitivity, down-regulated enzymes essential in glycolipid biosynthesis and were up-regulated enzymes involved in fatty acid (FA) catabolism (22) or its role in increase FA consumption through increase physical activity. This outcome of the present study disagreed with other studies which found no such difference in TG level after taking L-carnitine (22-24), while other studies agreed with this study outcome (25).

5. CONCLUSION

The present study was concluded that the administration of L-carnitine as an adjuvant supplement at a dose 1000mg twice daily for 3 successive months had a benefit effect on the triglyceride level in the T2DM patients with dyslipidemia, meanwhile, non-significant changes were observed on the levels of TC, HDL-C, and LDL-C.

6. CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

We hereby declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this research article.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Data have been obtained from El-beida Diabetic Center, Libya. We would like to express our appreciation and thanks to all the participants in this research study.

8. AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Author NAMI designed the study and wrote the protocol. Author YSEM wrote the manuscript and managed the literature searches. Author AAMS conducted the patient interviews and collected the data. Author HSH performed all the statistical analyses. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

9. ETHICS

All participants provided written permission and consent before collecting data to conduct this research study.

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